

ABOUT COLLEGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *The development of intellectual culture is very important for students of pedagogical colleges, since it provides them with the necessary skills and thinking to act in a constantly developing world. This article examines the mechanisms that can be used among students of pedagogical colleges to develop intellectual culture in innovative ways.*

Key words: *intellectual culture, innovative methods, pedagogical college, critical thinking, creativity, collaborative learning.*

О ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ В КОЛЛЕДЖЕ

Аннотация. *Развитие интеллектуальной культуры очень важно для студентов педагогических колледжей, поскольку оно обеспечивает их необходимыми навыками и мышлением для действий в постоянно развивающемся мире. В данной статье рассматриваются механизмы, которые могут быть использованы студентами педагогических колледжей для развития интеллектуальной культуры инновационными способами.*

Ключевые слова: *интеллектуальная культура, инновационные методы, педагогический колледж, критическое мышление, креативность, совместное обучение.*

Encouraging critical thinking: introducing students to activities and assignments that require data analysis, evaluation, and synthesis. Emphasize the importance of questioning assumptions, thinking independently, and considering multiple perspectives. Promoting creativity: give students the opportunity to solve creative problems and engage in the study of ideas. Assign projects that allow students to develop their own solutions or develop innovative teaching and teaching methods. Pedagogical mechanisms imply various strategies, approaches and techniques used in teaching and teaching processes to facilitate effective learning. These mechanisms aim to foster active participation, critical thinking, and meaningful learning experiences for students.

Here are some general pedagogical mechanisms:

- Active learning: this approach encourages students to actively participate in the learning process through discussions, group activities, problem-solving tasks, hands-on experiences and life programs. This increases student activity and deepens understanding.
- Inquiry-based learning: in this mechanism, students explore topics by asking questions, conducting investigations, and seeking solutions. It encourages critical thinking, problem solving, and the development of research skills.
- Cooperative education: this mechanism involves collaborative group work in which students work together to achieve a common goal. It promotes teamwork, communication skills and peer learning.
- Problem-based learning: students are presented with real problems or scenarios and tasked with finding solutions. It enhances critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and the application of knowledge in practical situations.

Teaching at the college represents a phase of the educational process in the Uzbek system. The college, as one of the medium-sized educational institutions, is another way in which one educational process that continues to receive higher education and increases the observation of higher educational institutions has come to the medium-sized educational institutions in Uzbekistan.

The colleges observe general education program, computer and electronics, economics, Lyceum and residential areas, chemistry, biology and other fields of study. In the educational process, one teacher, textbooks, laboratories and collective resources can be used for each subject.

The college is a more convenient way to offer students opportunities to attend higher education institutions. To propose these guidelines, it is necessary to contact the normalization Commission of colleges and board them with the documents of their students. Colleges receive an impressive passport and may require guides and exams to accept students.

Teaching at the college is an event-an airplane that aims to increase and prepare knowledge. The main tasks of teaching are to increase the scientific knowledge of students, develop excellent professional and skills, use new technologies and methodologies, introduce knowledge and skills of students, provide employment in the professional field and determine professional international cooperation.

The teaching environment at the college has expanded subject collections, which prepare students for a short period of time in the professional field. For example, there may be areas such as business, technology, culture, medicine, etc. The curricula offer students the opportunity to get the best education through apprenticeships, laboratory work, practices, research and projects.

The teaching system at the college is life-purpose, highly qualified, and the owner of an unappreciated experience is focused on training students as professional employees who are taking hours. Students struggle with their loved ones and family by gaining professional careers by improving their knowledge in a particular field, becoming members of a population of interest and interest in society, and fulfilling a parental role.

The success of teaching at the college should have a complete set of opportunities developed jointly by students, teachers, administrators and partners. Continuing education-ensuring performance, improving the quality of teaching, balancing scientific research, using new technologies and methods can be of great importance.

Extensive research supports the effectiveness of these mechanisms in promoting intellectual culture among students. Research has shown that developing critical thinking skills stimulates higher levels of cognitive processes and improves academic performance. Combining technology in an educational setting enhances activity, motivation, and access to information. Collaborative learning facilitates active student participation and improves problem-solving skills. Stimulating research and inquiry develops intellectual interest, deepens subject knowledge, and develops analytical thinking skills.

The development of intellectual culture among students of pedagogical colleges in innovative ways is very important for their personal and professional growth. Pedagogical colleges can create a favorable environment for intellectual growth by implementing mechanisms such as critical thinking, creativity, collaborative learning, technology integration, research and inquiry, mentoring, community engagement, and continuous professional development. Through these

mechanisms, students acquire the necessary skills and thinking to develop in a constantly changing world, contributing intellectually to lifelong learners and society.

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